

SOME ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES OF ETHNIC AND ETHNOGRAPHIC GROUPS IN THE AREA OF SURKHAN OASIS

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Abstract. *The given article presents the studies on the economic characteristics of some ethno-ethnographic groups in Surkhan oasis, formed in different historical periods. Natural and geographical conditions of Surkhan oasis where inhabitants are predominantly Uzbek and Tajik-speaking Chigatoys, Karluks, Barlos, Turks, Kaltatoys, Kungirat peoples, mountain peoples engaged in various economic activities. The location of ethno-ethnographic groups, such as Tagalogs, Yuzes are analyzed on the basis of scientific literature and sources. It was also believed that they specialize in types of agriculture suitable for the natural conditions of their place of residence.*

Keywords: *agriculture, ethnoterritorial, ethnographic unit, Tokharistan, lalmi, obi, deymi, kayraki, tramoj, reservoir, canal, chigatoys, gardening, Karabakh, Zarabog, Novbog.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that the population of Surkhan oasis is ethnically complex due to its location on the border with different peoples and nationalities. Representatives of different nationalities, Uzbeks, Tajiks, Turkmens, Arabs, Afghans and other ethnic groups live in close proximity to each other or in a mixed state. In addition, although the sedentary population of the oasis and the ethnic components that migrated at different times form ethnic units close to each other, they differ in their origin, facial structure, dialects, economic culture, way of life, customs and clans.

Literature Review. The works of such ethnographers as L.P. Potapov, M.V. Sazonova, G.P. Snesev, N.G. Borozna, B.Kh. Shoniyozov, I. Khidoyatov and Kh. Toshev present research on the traditional economy of Uzbek people. A number of books have been written about the economic and cultural traditions of Uzbek people, their development and regional characteristics. In particular, among them are the research works of S.N. Gabilov, U.S. Abdullayev, A.A. Boriyev, F.Sh. Tursunov, A.R. Kurbanov, Z.S. Turdimuradov.

Research Methodology. The following scientific research methods were used in writing the article: historical analysis, comparative analysis, field data collection, interviews and questionnaires.

Analysis and Results. The inhabitants of Surkhan oasis differ from other historical and cultural regions of our country. There are also some differences between some small and large settlements. Taking into account the climatic and natural conditions of the area where each ethnic and ethnographic group is located, their local features have formed in their life, economic and material culture [1, 66-67].

In the mountainous and foothill areas of the oasis, near the river, there lived a sedentary population engaged in agriculture and gardening, and a semi-sedentary population, where livestock farming was the leading one. The Tajiks lived mainly in the mountainous regions, the

semi-settled Uzbeks - in the low-mountain semi-steppe regions and flat steppes, and the mixed population - in the foothills and mountain slopes [2, 4].

Agriculture in Surkhan oasis, depending on the natural and geographical conditions, is divided into three parts: 1) irrigated agriculture; 2) mountain and foothill regions specializing in dry farming, horticulture and viticulture; 3) steppe grain and desert agriculture.

The existence of a specific distribution of types of agriculture among many ethnic groups of the oasis is reflected in the data on their ethnoterritorial location. The inhabitants of the oasis, primarily engaged in agriculture, were distributed in different places according to economic conditions, and in certain areas they were engaged in types of agriculture suitable for the natural conditions of their place of residence. Based on the collected materials, we will dwell on them in more detail below. The Chigatoys live mainly in areas near rivers, on plains and in the foothills suitable for agriculture. The main occupation of the Chigatoys is gardening, viticulture, irrigation and dry farming. I. Khidoyatov noted that the Chigatays, who lived in such large villages as Dashnabad (formerly Dashtinovad), Shakhkishlok, Gazarak, Dekhikalandar and Irman in Sariosiyo and Denov districts, had extensive experience in agricultural science [5, 124-133].

It is worth mentioning that S. Tursunov and E. Gabilov conditionally divide the Chigatay villages living in the southern part of the oasis into three groups [7, 145-146]. The first group includes villages located on the eastern slopes of the Kohitang Mountains, such as Sherdzhon, Vandoba, Zarabog, Karabog, Poshhord, Chakob, Khatak, Kyzylolma, Laylagon and Korizot. The residents of these villages used spring and Korizot water for gardening, viticulture, vegetable growing, field work, and sowed grain crops on dry lands [8, 45]. Chigatoy is divided into Uzbek-speaking and Tajik-speaking groups. At the end of the 19th century, topographer Petrov wrote that the residents of the villages of Shakhkishlak and Dashtinovad were Tajiks and Uzbeks [9, 99]. A list compiled in 1924 noted that the residents of the villages of Shakhkishlak and Dashtinovad were Tajiks [10, 16-17].

The Chigatoys, who lived in Samarkand, were engaged in irrigated and dry farming, gardening, cocoon breeding and cattle breeding. They mastered the cultivation of pomegranate in Samarkand, brought pomegranate cuttings to the newly resettled places and began to plant pomegranate here as well. Dashnabad was famous for its pomegranates.

According to N. A. Mayev, "Dashnabad, a relatively large and rich village is famous for its excellent-tasting pomegranates" [11, 124-133]. The residents of this village not only grow pomegranates, but also bury the pomegranates in the pits and keep them clean until May. Chigatoy's agricultural products were sold at the village market. Market days in Dashnabad coincided with other trade centers of the region [2, 224]. Yuz lived side by side with Kungirats in the middle and upper parts of Surkhan oasis. B. Karmisheva notes that their area of residence extends to the eastern edge of the Hissar Valley [11, 203].

According to the results of zoning conducted in 1924, 2,715 yuzes were registered in the upper reaches of Surkhandarya. In addition, I. P. Magidovich reported that most of 23,580 people in the village of Mirshodi came from the group of Turkmen yuzes [5, 133-139]. The yuzes live in irrigated areas near water sources convenient for agriculture, and agriculture is the basis of their economy. They mainly have extensive experience in growing rice. It is noted that Tajiks of the oasis mastered rice cultivation. People plowed the land with huge hoes weighing 8-10 kilograms. Physically strong people could use such a large working tool. These hoes were brought from Samarkand, and in Sariosiya and Uzun districts they were called "chimbur" (grass, i.e. fire cutter).

Such hoes were not used later [2, 78]. The Barlos are mainly Uzbek-Chigatoy and Tajik villages such as Jonchekka, Namuna in Uzun district, Dashnobad, Kudugly, Shakishlok and Karabandi in Sariosiya district, in Karatog-Darya basin, as well as in Shonsoy, Sangardak along the Khazorbog canal, Chimtepa in the east, who lived in a mixed way. The Barlos, living in this area also call themselves Barlos Turks. The Barlos moved to the Denov, Uzun and Sariosiya districts 350-400 years ago [5, 28].

Definitely, the Barloes were engaged in agriculture, gardening and viticulture. The Chigatoys, who lived near them, taught them gardening. In Surkhan oasis, the Dormans lived together with other clans in the village of Khodzhaki in Sherabad district (located on the right tributary of Sherabaddarya). It has also been established that they lived in the villages of Kholchayan, Faizabad, Serkharakat, Jiidabulok, Anorbulok and Pistamozor. Their origin is Kabadiyan (Tajikistan), some of them moved to Sariosiyo and Denov districts 255-300 years ago [12, 204-205]. Some of them associated their arrival in the oasis with Shaibanikhan [13, 12]. They were engaged in agriculture on irrigated and arid lands. During the Soviet period, farmers began to engage in other types of agriculture, in particular, agriculture and gardening [14, 16]. Initially, it was noted that some villages in Uzun district were inhabited by the Doromans, but in the 1960s their number exceeded 15. Kungirat flowers are widespread throughout the oasis and are divided into several small seeds. A number of research works have been carried out on the seeds of kungirat and their genealogy has been compiled. Settlements of the Kungirat are located on the banks of Baysundarya, Sherobdarya, Amu Darya and Surkhandarya rivers. It is densely located in the northern and southwestern parts of Surkhan oasis [15, 329].

According to the 1926 census, it was established that the Kungirat lived in the Karatog-Darya basin, in the upper part of the oasis and in Bobotog [16, 10]. They lived together with Tajiks in the upper part of the oasis, in Sangardak, Changlok, Bogcha and other villages of the mountainous regions. They lived in separate villages in Sariosiyo, Denov, Dashnabad, Sarijoy and Yurchi. Also, the population of the villages of Munchak, Chilanzor, Toda and Gumatak of Baysun district is mainly Kungirat. The Kungirat, who lived in Sariosiya and Denov districts, migrated from Dehkhanaabad (Kashkadarya) 280-290 years ago due to the lack of pastures and suitable land in Dehkhanaabad, as well as the onset of famine [5, 128].

Additionally, folk tales also provide important information when studying the history of the traditional economic activity of the Kungirats. For example, in the saga "Alpomish" in this regard, sedentary Kuhirs engaged in agriculture and nomadic Kuhirs engaged in livestock breeding are mentioned [17, 1]. Until the beginning of the 20th century, they were not engaged in agriculture, especially irrigated agriculture and were mainly engaged in cattle breeding. As a result of the development of Sherabad deserts, the Kungirats left their old places and were resettled in newly formed communities and state farms and began to engage in agriculture [18, 98]. A large group of Karluks is located mainly on the southern slopes of the Hisar Range, they are also called Turkic Karluks. In Sariosiyo district, the Karluks lived in the villages of Togchiyan, Baykishlok, Zagnivot, Pozilkochdi, Kolmozor, Cholmiyan, Sarizoro, Buyropush and Neloba and were called "five hundred house Karluks" [19, 481-490].

In Soviet times, the Karluks were engaged in cotton growing, gardening, cocooning on collective farms, and also worked in Shargun coal mine [5, 124-133].

They skillfully cultivated the land, sowed spring and autumn wheat, barley, as well as rice, vegetables and other crops, and mastered their own economic culture [19, 49].

Their large village of Karluk is located on the bank of Khalgayar River. At the beginning of the 20th century, 120 farms (636 people) were registered. Its population is ethnically mixed, but most of them are Karagi. At the beginning of the 20th century, the Ipok Karluks (Karluk village) led a sedentary lifestyle on the bank of Ipok River in Altinsoy district and were mainly engaged in agriculture and gardening. In terms of anthropological, linguistic features and customs, Ipok Karluks are similar to the Karluks living in Mubarak district of Kashkadarya oasis [20, 152]. The Karluks living in Sariosiyo and Uzun districts led a semi-sedentary lifestyle at the beginning of the 20th century. The Katagans lived in the villages of Khatak and Khodjangan on the slopes of Mount Kohitang, in the villages of Olachopon and Kayrok on Baysun ridge, in the villages of Sangardak (with an admixture of Tajiks), Changlok, Bogcha, on the right bank of Surkhandarya River. Before the Soviet era, the Tagalogs were engaged in irrigated and dry farming, gardening. In the oasis, blackbirds live mainly in the village of Khomkon in Sherabad district. After the resettlement of 1949-1953, the Karakalpaks from Khomkon settled in "Surkhan" and "Navoi" in Jarkurgan district, Tallimaron in Angor district, "Besh Khorekh" in Kumkurgan district, Okhunboboev in Kizirik district, "Pakhtakor" in Bandikhan district of Sherabad, also, "Kallamazor", "Tallashkhan" district, "Chilanzor" Baysun district and Muzrabod district. They live in the regions called "Navbakhor" and "Navoi" [21, 39-43]. At present time, the basis of their economy is agriculture.

Moreover, Tajiks living in the mountainous parts of the oasis belong to two groups: the first is the Kohistanis (mountain), those who consider themselves aborigines, and the second group includes velayats or Hisars who came from different places. The Kohistan Tajiks, belonging to the first group, live in the small mountain villages of Fypit Shorut, Karsh, Tamshush, Choch, Nilu, Zevar and other villages, and the velayats or Hisoris, belonging to the second group, live in Khufar, Sina, Malau, Sariosiyo, Yurchi, Dehkalandar and in other villages. As a result of the exploitation of Beshkotan, Istara and Muzrabod deserts during the Soviet period, residents of the mountainous and foothill areas of the oasis were resettled to these new lands.

Due to internal migrations, most of the clans living in the oasis began to mix with each other, which led to the population engaging in mixed economic activities. Besides that, in the years before the World War, the Soviet government forcibly resettled the population from Fergana Valley to the lands of the recently developed Surkhan oasis, and they mastered cotton cultivation. Those, who were copied as "cotton masters" or "experimenters" were called "farganists" by local residents [22, 15-16]. They were placed in Termez, Kumkurgan, Denov and Shorchin districts. As a result, economic exchange processes began to take place in these regions.

Conclusion and recommendations. In conclusion, it should be suggested that the natural and geographical climatic conditions of Surkhan oasis have created the opportunity for the peoples living in this territory to engage in various economic activities since ancient times. Ethnic groups that moved to this territory in different historical periods influenced the economic culture of the population or themselves adopted the farming traditions characteristic of this territory. In the 20th century, the main ethnocultural processes in Surkhan oasis intensified - mutual cultural influence, rapprochement of the sedentary and cattle-breeding population, the process of partial assimilation. Undoubtedly, the process of settlement and disappearance of clan traditions in places of compact residence in the oasis of semi-sedentary Uzbeks and Turks continued gradually. Despite the fact that in such Uzbek clans as Kungirov, Karluk, Lakai, Dormon, up until the 1930s, agriculture was widespread, they retained elements of a semi-sedentary way of life and tribal system.

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